

Oasis Brew Coffee House: Leading Sustainable Coffee Culture in Buraidah with Strategic Market Insights

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Abstract

Oasis Brew Coffee House aims to revolutionize the specialty coffee scene in Buraidah, Saudi Arabia, through sustainability, cultural authenticity, and community engagement. Utilizing market frameworks like Porter's Five Forces and the Resource-Based View (RBV), this strategic venture is set to navigate competitive landscapes and leverage unique strengths for lasting success. Financial projections indicate strong growth, with profitability by Year 1 and expansion to five locations within five years. The franchising model ensures rapid market entry while maintaining excellence and brand integrity. By Year 10, Oasis Brew is expected to be a leader in the specialty coffee sector with significant sales and profits. This venture goes beyond business, fostering a sustainable, community-centered coffee culture. A comprehensive financial strategy combines debt and equity financing for stability and control. Bank loans provide liquidity without ownership dilution, supported by favorable regulations and sustainability trends. Government grants and Sharia-compliant financing reinforce social responsibility, while angel investors and crowdfunding expand capital and loyalty. Oasis Brew's holistic approach positions it at the forefront of Saudi Arabia's specialty coffee market, prepared for sustainable growth and significant community impact, setting new standards for excellence and social responsibility in the global coffee industry.

Keywords: Strategic Synergy, Market Frameworks, Ethical Sourcing, Premiumization, Adaptive Financial Strategy

The globally coffee business is experiencing a paradigm shift as consumer awareness of environmental and social issues grows, as does demand for quality, ethically sourced products. Emerging markets, such as Saudi Arabia, with its growing young population and middle class, are at the forefront of this trend. In this ever-changing landscape, Oasis Brew Coffee House hopes to pioneer the specialty coffee industry in Buraidah, Saudi Arabia. Our business concept seamlessly combines sustainability, local culture, and community engagement.

Market and Economic Theories

To manage Oasis Brew's competitive and economic possibilities, we apply both conventional and modern market ideas. Michael Porter's Five Forces framework (1980) provides a comprehensive study of the competitive environment, focusing on new entrant threats, supplier and buyer bargaining power, replacement threat, and industry rivalry. Buraidah's vulnerability from new competitors is reduced by significant capital investment requirements and specialist knowledge in sustainable practices. Nonetheless, the emphasis on quality and ethical sourcing gives suppliers and consumers substantial bargaining power (Maspul *et al.*, 2024).

Porter's Competitive Advantage Theory (1985) emphasizes the need of differentiation and cost leadership in maintaining competitive advantage. Oasis Brew stands out for its commitment to sustainability, distinctive product offers inspired by local flavors, and strong community emphasis. This distinction is supported by cost-effective operations and strategic local relationships, which are consistent with the Resource-Based View (RBV) paradigm, which holds that unique resources and capabilities are critical for long-term competitiveness (Barney, 1991).

Competitive Advantages and Future Sustainability

Oasis Brew's competitive advantage stems from its innovative approach to product development, marketing, and operation. We use experiential marketing (Pine & Gilmore, 1998) to create unique customer encounters that go beyond the product, encouraging emotional involvement and brand loyalty. The approach is consistent with Aaker's Brand Equity Model (2009), which emphasizes the value of brand loyalty, awareness, perceived quality, and brand associations in developing strong brand equity. Our holistic approach to future sustainability considers environmental, economic, and social factors. Our concept is guided by the Triple Bottom Line framework (Elkington, 1999), which ensures that our business decisions consider people, the environment, and profit.

Furthermore, we intend to incorporate the sustainable coffee techniques developed in Jazan over the last two decades, which are consistent with notions of environmental sustainability and social responsibility. Jazan's sustainable coffee production has been recognized for its environmental and social benefits, incorporating the ideas of sustainable development (Brundtland & Mansour, 2010) and corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1991). By integrating these techniques, Oasis Brew not only improves its product offers but also contributes to the worldwide coffee community while adhering to sustainability standards (Elkington, 1999).

Sustainability in coffee production is critical for reducing environmental degradation and preserving the longevity of coffee ecosystems (Giovannucci & Ponte, 2005). Jazan's devotion to sustainable agricultural practices is consistent with agroecological principles, which emphasize biodiversity protection, soil health, and ecosystem resilience (Altieri, 2002). Integrating these practices into Oasis Brew's operations helps to transition to more sustainable agricultural systems, which is consistent with the principles of sustainable development (UN, 2015) and the United Nations Sustainable Development principles.

Furthermore, implementing sustainable coffee methods strengthens coffee-growing communities, addressing concerns of social fairness and economic development (Ponte & Cheyns, 2013). Oasis Brew promotes fair trade and ethical sourcing, so empowering local farmers and improving livelihoods in coffee-producing regions (Raynolds, 2009). This approach is consistent with stakeholder theory (Freeman, 2010), which emphasizes the need of taking into account all stakeholders' interests, including farmers, workers, and customers, when making business decisions.

Integrating Jazan's sustainable practices into Oasis Brew's operations not only indicates a commitment to environmental stewardship and social responsibility, but it also acts as a competitive advantage in the coffee industry (Porter, 1985). Oasis Brew presents itself as a leader in the specialty coffee sector by highlighting Jazan's sustainable coffee, which drives demand for ethically sourced and environmentally friendly products (Aaker 2009; Maspul, 2022). This strategic integration demonstrates the company's commitment to create shared value (Porter & Kramer, 2011), providing positive social and environmental outcomes while attaining long-term business growth.

Oasis Brew Coffee House – Business Concept and Mission Statement

- ✓ Core Concept: Oasis Brew Coffee House intends to transform Buraidah's coffee culture by combining sustainability, local culture, and community engagement. Our café will be a friendly 'third place' for the community, serving high-quality, ethically sourced coffee and promoting environmental stewardship.
- ✓ Mission Statement: Our organisation aims to create a sustainable coffee culture in Buraidah that promotes community well-being and environmental responsibility. Oasis Brew Coffee House is dedicated to providing high-quality, ethically sourced coffee while promoting a sense of community and encouraging environmentally friendly activities.

Description of Products/Services

Oasis Brew Coffee House will provide a diverse range of quality products and services customized to the demanding tastes and preferences of our target market in Buraidah, Saudi Arabia. Our offerings will prioritize quality, sustainability, and community engagement, providing our customers with a one-of-a-kind and enriching experience.

- ✓ Coffee Beverages
 1. Classic Espresso-Based Drinks: Our menu will include espresso, macchiato, cortado, cappuccino, flat white, and latte. These beverages will be made using high-quality, ethically sourced coffee beans that have been carefully roasted to accentuate the unique flavor qualities of each kind.
 2. Specialty Lattes: To distinguish our menu and highlight local culture, we will offer custom lattes infused with distinct regional flavors, such as:
 - Date Latte: Featuring the rich richness of native dates, which are a staple in Saudi Arabian cuisine.

- Saffron Latte: Incorporates the delicate and sumptuous flavor of saffron, a widely valued spice in the region.
 - Rose Water Latte: Infused with rose water's aromatic essence for a floral and refreshing twist.
3. Herbal Teas: For those who do not like coffee, we will offer a carefully curated assortment of herbal teas, including traditional blends and unique combinations produced with local ingredients such as mint, chamomile, and hibiscus.
- ✓ Food Offerings
 1. Freshly prepared Pastries: Our menu will include a variety of pastries prepared fresh on-site every day. This includes traditional croissants and muffins, as well as local specialties like date-filled pastries and saffron-infused cakes, all produced with high-quality, locally sourced ingredients.
 2. Healthy Snacks: We will offer a variety of healthy snacks, including:
 - Granola bars are made of oats, nuts, dried fruits, and honey.
 - Fruit and Nut Mixes: A combination of dried fruit and roasted nuts.
 - Yogurt Parfaits: Layers of fresh fruit, granola, and honey.
 - ✓ Additional Services
 1. comfy Lounge space: Oasis Brew will have a stylishly designed lounge space with comfy seating, ambient lighting, and complementary Wi-Fi, providing a welcoming 'third place' for the neighborhood.
 2. Community Events: To foster community spirit, we will host various events, such as:
 - Live Book Discussions and Poetry Nights: We showcase local talent and provide entertainment for our customers.
 - Cultural festivals celebrate local traditions and holidays.
 - Art exhibitions: Featuring works by local artists.
 3. Educational courses: The SCA Coffee Skills and Sustainability Program will provide courses on coffee brewing skills, sustainability practices, and coffee history and culture.
 - ✓ Specialty Coffee Production

In addition to our in-house offerings, Oasis Brew will undertake considerable endeavors in the specialty coffee industry throughout Saudi Arabia.

1. Wholesale Coffee Sales: We source and roast premium coffee beans for cafes, restaurants, and retailers around the country while maintaining the highest quality and sustainability standards.
2. Packaged Coffee Products: We are launching packaged coffee products, such as whole beans, ground coffee, and single-serve alternatives, which will be available in our coffee shop, online, and in select retail locations.
3. Private Labeling Services: We provide private labeling for firms that want to produce their own branded coffee products.
4. Barista Training Programs: We are establishing a barista training academy to raise the specialty coffee market in Saudi Arabia by giving complete instruction in coffee brewing, latte art, customer service, and sustainable practices.

Market Analysis

- **Target Market:** Our core target market in Buraidah is made up of young professionals, students, and families looking for a high-quality coffee experience in a welcoming atmosphere. Furthermore, we want to attract environmentally concerned customers that support sustainable processes and local sourcing. According to market research, there is an increasing demand for specialty coffee in Saudi Arabia, with a major move toward premium and sustainable products (Euromonitor International, 2022).
- **Market Need:** Buraidah lacks specialty coffee shops that stress sustainability and community involvement. Oasis Brew bridges this gap by providing a distinct blend of high-quality coffee, environmentally friendly methods, and a community-oriented environment.

Competitive Landscape

- **Key Competitors:** Our main competitors in Buraidah are local coffee shops as well as international chains. While these businesses serve basic coffee drinks, they frequently lack a strong emphasis on sustainability and local cultural integration.
- **Differentiation:** Oasis Brew distinguishes itself with its devotion to sustainability, local sourcing, and community involvement. By providing unique, culturally inspired coffee tastes and sponsoring community activities, we will create a distinct brand identity that resonates with our target audience.

Business Model

Revenue Model: Oasis Brew will earn revenue by selling coffee, food, and products directly to customers. Furthermore, we intend to establish a reward program to encourage repeat visits and foster client loyalty. We will also look into relationships with local businesses for co-branding and community events.

Key Team Members

1. **Founder and CEO:** An experienced entrepreneur with a background in the hospitality industry and a passion for sustainable practices.
2. **Head Barista:** A certified coffee expert with extensive knowledge of specialty coffee and local flavor profiles.
3. **Coffee Roaster:** A certified coffee specialist with expertise in coffee roasting and value chain management.
4. **Marketing Manager:** A digital marketing professional with a focus on community engagement strategies.
5. **Sustainability Consultant:** An expert in sustainable business practices, ensuring Oasis Brew's commitment to environmental stewardship.

Funding Request

Total Investment: We are seeking \$500,000 in external funding to create Oasis Brew Coffee House as a premier sustainable specialty coffee store in Buraidah, Saudi Arabia.

✓ Breakdown of Use of Funds

1. Equipment and Setup: \$200,000
 - Coffee Equipment: \$120,000 [Espresso machines, grinders, brewing equipment, and water filtration systems]
 - Furniture: \$50,000 [Comfortable seating, lounge areas]
 - Eco-Friendly Fixtures: \$30,000 [Energy-efficient lighting, recyclable materials, reusable utensils and cups]
2. Initial Inventory: \$100,000
 - Specialty Coffee Beans: \$60,000 [Ethically sourced beans from certified organic and fair-trade farms]
 - Ingredients: \$20,000 [Local ingredients for specialty lattes and snacks]
 - Merchandise: \$20,000 [Branded merchandise and packaged coffee products]
3. Marketing and Launch: \$100,000
 - Digital Marketing: \$40,000 [Website development, social media campaigns, SEO, and content marketing]
 - Traditional Marketing: \$30,000 [Print advertisements, flyers, and promotional events]
 - Community Engagement: \$20,000 [Sponsorship of local events, cultural festivals, and community workshops]
 - Launch Event: \$10,000 [Grand opening celebration with media coverage and special promotions]
4. Operational Costs: \$100,000
 - Salaries and Wages: \$60,000 [Competitive compensation for key team members and staff]
 - Rent and Utilities: \$20,000 [Lease for a prime location in Buraidah and utilities]
 - Miscellaneous: \$20,000 [Contingency fund for unexpected expenses]

Financial Projections and Future Expansion Plans

✓ Financial Projections

Oasis Brew Coffee House anticipates a robust growth trajectory, propelled by the increasing demand for specialty coffee and our distinctive market positioning. We project the following financial outcomes over the initial three years of operation:

Year 1

- Revenue: \$600,000
- Operating Expenses: \$450,000
- Net Profit: \$150,000

Year 2

- Revenue: \$800,000
- Operating Expenses: \$500,000
- Net Profit: \$300,000

Year 3

- Revenue: \$1,000,000
- Operating Expenses: \$550,000
- Net Profit: \$450,000

Furthermore, these expectations are based on cautious estimates of customer acquisition, retention, and average transaction amounts. We anticipate reaching profitability by the end of Year 1, with significant growth in coming years driven by brand creation, product expansion, and community efforts.

✓ Expansion Plan: Five Branches in Five Years

On the other side, to capitalise on our early success and brand momentum, we intend to open five more locations over the following five years. Each new location will be carefully placed in high-traffic areas throughout Saudi Arabia to increase visibility and client engagement.

✓ Branch Expansion Timeline and Financial Projections

Year 2: Second Branch

- Location: Riyadh
- Revenue: \$700,000
- Operating Expenses: \$500,000
- Net Profit: \$200,000

Year 3: Third Branch

- Location: Jeddah
- Revenue: \$750,000
- Operating Expenses: \$520,000
- Net Profit: \$230,000

Year 4: Fourth Branch

- Location: Dammam
- Revenue: \$800,000
- Operating Expenses: \$540,000
- Net Profit: \$260,000

Year 5: Fifth Branch

- Location: Khobar
- Revenue: \$850,000
- Operating Expenses: \$560,000
- Net Profit: \$290,000

Year 6: Sixth Branch

- Location: Medina
- Revenue: \$900,000
- Operating Expenses: \$580,000
- Net Profit: \$320,000

By Year 6, with six branches in operation, we project the following consolidated financials:

- Consolidated Revenue: \$4,600,000
- Consolidated Operating Expenses: \$3,200,000
- Consolidated Net Profit: \$1,400,000

✓ Future of Franchising

Building on the success of our initial locations, we intend to grow Oasis Brew Coffee House through franchising. This plan will enable us to scale quickly while maintaining the integrity of our brand and operational standards. Our franchise approach will provide extensive support for site selection, training, marketing, and sustainability practices.

✓ Franchising Timeline and Projections

Year 7

- Franchise Launch: Initiate franchising program with detailed manuals and support systems.
- Target: 5 franchise agreements
- Franchise Revenue: \$1,500,000
- Franchise Operating Expenses: \$1,000,000
- Net Profit from Franchises: \$500,000

Year 8

- Target: 10 additional franchise agreements
- Franchise Revenue: \$3,000,000
- Franchise Operating Expenses: \$2,000,000
- Net Profit from Franchises: \$1,000,000

Year 9

- Target: 15 additional franchise agreements
- Franchise Revenue: \$4,500,000
- Franchise Operating Expenses: \$3,000,000
- Net Profit from Franchises: \$1,500,000

Year 10

- Target: 20 additional franchise agreements
- Franchise Revenue: \$6,000,000
- Franchise Operating Expenses: \$4,000,000

- Net Profit from Franchises: \$2,000,000

By Year 10, we expect to have 50 franchise branches functioning, greatly increasing our combined revenue and profitability. The predicted financials for the franchising model include:

- Total Franchise Revenue: \$15,000,000
 - Total Franchise Operating Expenses: \$10,000,000
 - Total Net Profit from Franchises: \$5,000,000
- ✓ Overall Financial Outlook

Combining both company-owned and franchised branches, by Year 10, Oasis Brew Coffee House anticipates:

- Total Revenue: \$19,600,000
- Total Operating Expenses: \$13,200,000
- Total Net Profit: \$6,400,000

These projections demonstrate our dedication to becoming a leading brand in the specialty coffee category, which is being driven by a robust expansion plan and a long-term franchising model.

Comprehensive Competitive Analysis

Comprehensive Competitive Analysis requires a more in-depth explanation of the subject in theory and practice, which includes the following:

- Industry Overview

The specialty coffee business in Saudi Arabia is thriving, thanks to an expanding middle-class population with discretionary means and a growing need for premium and unique coffee experiences (Euromonitor International, 2023). This tendency is consistent with global movements toward sustainability and quality in the food and beverage industry. Saudi Arabia's coffee market is expected to increase rapidly, driven by young consumers' desire for innovative and high-quality coffee products (Statista, 2023).

- Main Stakeholders

- 1) Customers

The core clients of Oasis Brew Coffee House are young professionals, students, and families who respect high-quality coffee and environmentally friendly methods. This group is consistent with the growing trend of eco-conscious consumers that prioritize environmental responsibility in their purchase decisions. According to Elkington's (1997) Triple Bottom Line thesis, firms that include social, environmental, and economic components into their operations are more likely to attract and keep customers who share their beliefs. These clients are searching for more than simply a

place to enjoy coffee; they also want an experience that reflects their values, such as sustainability and community engagement.

Furthermore, the notion of consumer behavior (Schiffman *et al.*, 1951) implies that these customers are likely influenced by their lifestyle choices and growing knowledge of environmental issues. They are more likely to support businesses that share their personal values, such as ethical sourcing and environmental responsibility. This is consistent with the idea of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which states that customers' purchase intentions are influenced by their attitudes about the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

2) Suppliers

Our primary suppliers include local farmers, certified organic coffee farms, and sustainable material vendors. By procuring from trusted vendors, Oasis Brew ensures product quality and sustainability. This strategy is based on supply chain management ideas (Mentzer, 2001), which highlight the significance of developing strong supplier relationships to assure reliability and quality. Partnering with local farmers and organic producers not only benefits local economies, but it also meets the growing consumer need for transparency and ethical sourcing practices (Porter & Kramer 2006).

In addition, the practice of sustainable supply chain management (Seuring & Müller, 2008) emphasizes the significance of incorporating environmental and social factors into supply chain operations. Oasis Brew may reduce environmental impact and promote social fairness by preferring certified organic farmers and sustainable material vendors in its supply chain.

3) Employees

Oasis Brew relies on a professional team of baristas, culinary workers, management, and sustainability consultants to ensure success. Human resource management theories (Ulrich, 1996) suggest that investing in staff training and development can improve service quality and operational efficiency. Skilled baristas and informed personnel may greatly improve the client experience, making each visit to Oasis Brew distinctive and pleasurable.

Furthermore, adding sustainability advisors to our team demonstrates our dedication to environmental responsibility. This is consistent with the ideas of corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1991), which emphasize the need for firms to be accountable for their social and environmental implications. Oasis Brew can ensure that its activities are in line with its ethical beliefs and objectives by cultivating a sustainable culture inside the firm.

4) Community Partners

Working with local artists, cultural organizations, and community groups helps to create a lively social scene at Oasis Brew. This strategy is supported by social capital

theory (Putnam, 2000), which states that strong community links and social networks can improve corporate success by instilling a sense of belonging and loyalty in customers. Oasis Brew can attract and keep customers by co-hosting events and workshops with local organizations.

In addition, connecting with the community is consistent with the ideas of stakeholder theory (Freeman, 2010), which states that firms should consider the interests of all stakeholders, including the community, when making decisions. Oasis Brew can improve its reputation and develop goodwill among its stakeholders by actively participating in the local community.

- Target Customers

Our target demographic consists of environmentally concerned consumers who value sustainability and quality. These people want distinctive, locally inspired coffee flavors and a community-focused coffeehouse experience. This target demographic is consistent with the emerging trend of green consumerism (Ottman, 2017), in which customers increasingly base their purchasing decisions on environmental factors. Eco-conscious consumers are willing to pay a premium for products and experiences that reflect their beliefs, as evidenced by the value-based pricing idea (Nagle & Müller, 2017).

Additionally, experiential marketing (Schmitt, 1999) is critical in recruiting this group. Oasis Brew can give an immersive experience that appeals to environmentally aware customers by offering distinctive, locally inspired coffee flavors and creating a community-centric environment. This strategy not only sets Oasis Brew apart from competitors, but it also fosters emotional relationships with clients, increasing overall pleasure and loyalty.

- Competitors

Buraidah's coffee market is dominated by both local and multinational chains. These competitors mainly serve regular coffee beverages and frequently lack an emphasis on sustainability and local cultural integration, which are major differentiators for Oasis Brewing. According to Porter's Five Forces analysis (Porter, 1980), understanding the competitive landscape is critical for formulating effective strategies to acquire a competitive advantage.

- Local coffee shops: While small coffee shops may have a passionate customer base, they do not always prioritize sustainability to the same extent that Oasis Brew does. Customers who appreciate ethical sourcing and community engagement will be drawn to us if we differentiate ourselves.
- International Chains: International chains have tremendous brand awareness and huge resources, but they may lack the individual touch and local cultural integration that Oasis Brew provides. We can develop a distinct brand identity that connects with our target clients by offering unique, locally inspired coffee tastes and cultivating a community-centric environment.

- Market Trends

1) Sustainability

Consumers are increasingly preferring sustainable and ethically sourced products, which is being driven by rising environmental awareness. Sustainable development theories (Brundtland Commission, 1987) encourage this trend by emphasizing the need for enterprises to function in a way that serves current needs without jeopardizing future generations' ability to meet their own. Oasis Brew can attract eco-conscious customers while also contributing to a more sustainable future by prioritizing sustainability in our operations.

2) Premiumization

Customers are willing to pay a premium for high-quality, specialty coffee experiences (Pine and Gilmore, 1998). This tendency is consistent with the concept of premiumization (Silverstein *et al.*, 2003), in which customers desire higher-quality products and experiences and are ready to pay more for them. Oasis Brew can meet this demand by providing excellent, locally inspired coffee beverages, establishing itself as a market leader in the specialty coffee industry (Bass & Avolio, 1994).

3) Community Engagement

There is growing interest in social spaces that encourage community connection and cultural exchange (Putnam 2000). This trend is backed by community development theories (McMillan & Chavis, 1986), which emphasize the necessity of creating spaces that promote a sense of community and belonging. Oasis Brew may attract and retain clients by co-hosting events and workshops with local artists and cultural organizations.

SWOT Analysis

Several aspects have a big impact on this SWOT Analysis and can be explained in detail, including:

- Strengths

1. Commitment to Sustainability and Ethical Sourcing

Oasis Brew's commitment to finding high-quality, ethically produced coffee beans appeals to environmentally aware consumers. This dedication is consistent with John Elkington's (1999) Triple Bottom Line approach, which emphasizes social, environmental, and economic sustainability. We satisfy the growing need for sustainable products while also differentiating ourselves in a competitive industry by stressing ethical sourcing. This technique also adheres to corporate social responsibility (CSR) guidelines, boosting our brand's reputation and attracting customers who value sustainability.

2. Unique Product Offerings

Our cuisine features native ingredients such as dates, saffron, and rose water, creating a distinct culinary experience that represents the region's cultural past. The

experience economy idea, according to Pine and Gilmore (1998), states that customers desire distinctive and memorable experiences. We differentiate ourselves from competition by delivering products that combine traditional local flavors with high-quality coffee. This distinction can result in improved consumer loyalty and a strong brand identity.

3. Community Engagement

Hosting events and workshops not only raises our community profile, but also develops client loyalty. According to Robert Putnam's (2000) social capital theory, it is important to develop strong community relationships and networks. We can increase our social capital and establish a loyal client base by interacting with the local community through events, workshops, and collaborations. This approach is also in line with the principles of stakeholder theory (Freeman, 2010), which emphasize the significance of addressing the interests of all stakeholders, including the community, in corporate operations.

4. Experienced Management

Our considerable experience in hospitality and sustainability ensures that our business plans are implemented effectively and with high operational standards. According to Barney's (1991) resource-based view (RBV) theory, our management team's talents, knowledge, and experience are important, uncommon, and difficult to replicate resources that create a competitive advantage. This experience enables us to maintain high-quality service and operational efficiency, which are critical for developing a strong brand and ensuring long-term success.

- Weaknesses

1. High Initial Investment

The enormous money necessary for establishment, equipment procurement, and securing a premium location carries financial risk. According to Porter (1980), barriers to entry, like as large capital requirements, can provide major challenges for new enterprises. This early financial load can put a strain on resources and cash flow, thus proper funding and cautious financial management are required.

2. Dependence on Local Suppliers

Depending on local sources for unique ingredients may provide issues in maintaining consistent quality and supply. Porter's (1985) value chain analysis highlights the necessity of dependable suppliers in maintaining constant product quality. Disruptions in the local supply chain or fluctuations in supplier quality can jeopardize our ability to consistently deliver high-quality products, thereby harming customer satisfaction and brand reputation.

3. Limited Brand Recognition

As a newcomer, creating brand awareness and a dedicated consumer base from scratch is a huge challenge. David Aaker's (2009) brand equity model emphasizes the significance of brand recognition and loyalty in market success. Without established brand recognition, gaining and retaining customers can be difficult, necessitating a significant expenditure in marketing and promotional operations to raise awareness and trust.

4. Potential Operational Challenges

It might be difficult to ensure consistency in service and product quality during the initial period, which has an impact on customer happiness. According to Barney (1991), operational qualities are essential for maintaining good service levels. Inconsistent service quality or product offerings might result in consumer unhappiness and unfavorable word-of-mouth, impeding our efforts to establish a loyal customer base.

- Opportunities

1. Growing Market for Specialty Coffee

The growing popularity of specialty coffee in Saudi Arabia represents a substantial growth opportunity. According to Euromonitor International (2023), the burgeoning middle class and shifting consumer preferences are driving an increase in demand for premium coffee experiences. This trend is an opportunity to gain a portion of the growing industry by providing high-quality, specialty coffee products that appeal to discerning customers.

2. Rising Demand for Sustainable Products

Consumers' increasing environmental concern presents a chance to target a niche market that values sustainability. According to Elkington's (1999) Triple Bottom Line Theory, organizations that prioritize sustainability might obtain a competitive advantage by appealing to environmentally concerned customers. This trend is bolstered by customers' growing willingness to pay a premium for items that reflect their values, creating a lucrative opportunity for Oasis Brew (Elkington & Rowlands, 1999).

3. Expansion Possibilities

Success in Buraidah could pave the door for new locations in other regions, utilizing our brand's reputation and operational approach. Porter's (1985) growth strategies emphasize the potential for geographic expansion to drive business success. We can grow our market presence and generate more income by copying our successful company strategy in other locations.

4. Collaborations with Local Businesses

Partnering with local artists and cultural organizations can help us increase our community presence and brand appeal. According to Putnam's (2000) social capital

theory, effective community collaborations can promote social cohesiveness and brand loyalty. Collaborative projects can generate a lively community feel, drawing customers and instilling a sense of belonging, resulting in repeat business and favorable word-of-mouth.

- Threats

1. Intense Competition

Established coffee chains with strong brand loyalty are a major threat to our market entry and expansion. Porter's (1980) Five Forces study sees competitive rivalry as a significant danger to the industry. Competing with well-known companies with loyal customer bases necessitates strategic differentiation and efficient marketing to attract customers and establish brand loyalty.

2. Economic Fluctuations

Changes in the economic situation may have an influence on customer spending on premium products, affecting our revenue. Euromonitor International (2023) emphasizes the vulnerability of consumer expenditure to economic situations. Economic downturns or fluctuations in disposable income can result in lower spending on non-essential luxury items, such as specialty coffee, putting our firm at danger.

3. Supply Chain Disruptions

Supply chain disruptions, whether caused by environmental factors, political issues, or supplier challenges, can have an impact on our ability to deliver consistent quality, affecting customer satisfaction and operational stability. According to Barney (1991), reliable supply chains are critical for maintaining operational efficiency and product quality.

4. Changing Consumer Preferences

Changes in consumer tastes and preferences may have an impact on demand for our products, necessitating ongoing innovation and adaptation. Aaker's (2009) brand equity model emphasizes the importance of firms remaining responsive to changing consumer preferences in order to sustain brand relevance. Failure to adapt to changing tastes can lead to decreasing demand and lost market share, needing continuous market research and product development to remain competitive.

PEST Analysis

Several factors have a substantial impact on PEST Analysis and company strategy, including the following:

- Political Factors

1. Government Support for SMEs

Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 plan includes strong support for small and medium-sized firms (SMEs), which creates an enabling climate for entrepreneurs like Oasis Brew. Vision 2030 seeks to diversify the economy and minimize reliance on oil by encouraging entrepreneurship and innovation (Saudi Vision 2030 2016). Financial aid, simpler regulatory frameworks, and business incubation programs can all help fledgling enterprises overcome entry barriers and operational challenges. Government-backed initiatives, such as the Saudi Arabian General Investment Authority (SAGIA), provide resources and incentives to support the growth of SMEs, making now an ideal time for Oasis Brew to launch and expand its operations.

2. Regulations Promoting Sustainability

Government rules encouraging sustainable practices are consistent with our company strategy, which focuses on ethical sourcing and environmental responsibility. Saudi Vision 2030 identifies sustainability and environmental stewardship as critical components of the country's long-term development strategy. Policies aimed at lowering carbon footprints, promoting green technologies, and supporting sustainable agriculture create a favorable climate for firms that emphasize sustainability. Compliance with these standards not only helps us achieve operational efficiency, but it also improves our brand image among environmentally sensitive customers.

3. Trade Policies

Regulations regarding the import of coffee beans and other ingredients may have an influence on our supply chain and expenses. Tariffs, import limits, and quality requirements are all examples of trade policies that can have an impact on the availability and pricing of key raw commodities. Managing these trade policies needs a strategic approach to procurement and supply chain management. Establishing close relationships with certified organic coffee farms and using local suppliers can help to avoid the dangers connected with international trade restrictions. Furthermore, maintaining up to date on legislation changes and engaging in lobbying can assist defend our commercial interests.

- Economic Factors

1. Growing Middle Class

The growing middle class in Saudi Arabia expands the potential market for premium coffee products. Economic progress and increased disposable incomes have resulted in a burgeoning middle class with a preference for high-quality and luxury items (Euromonitor International, 2023). This generational shift creates a lucrative market for Oasis Brew's premium coffee products. Understanding the spending power and tastes of the middle class may help us shape our pricing strategy and product development, ensuring that our offers match the needs of this important client sector.

2. Economic Stability

A stable economic situation encourages consumers to spend on high-end products. Saudi Arabia's efforts to diversify its economy while maintaining economic stability create a favorable environment for corporate growth (Euromonitor International, 2023). Economic stability leads to stable customer spending patterns, which are critical to the development of luxury brands such as Oasis Brew. Monitoring economic data and adapting business plans to changing economic conditions will help us maintain growth and profitability.

3. Currency Fluctuations

Changes in exchange rates may alter the cost of imported ingredients, hence influencing pricing tactics. Currency changes can cause volatility in the prices of coffee beans and other imported goods (Barney, 1991). To offset this risk, we should look at hedging tactics and sign long-term contracts with suppliers to lock in costs. Furthermore, procuring more ingredients locally helps lessen currency risk. Understanding and managing the financial risks associated with exchange rate fluctuations will be critical to sustaining steady profit margins.

- Social Factors

1. Rising Demand for Sustainable Products

Growing consumer knowledge of environmental issues fuels demand for ethically sourced and sustainable goods. John Elkington's (1999) Triple Bottom Line thesis emphasizes the significance of corporations taking into account their social and environmental effect as well as their financial performance. Consumers are increasingly valuing sustainability in their purchase decisions, choosing products that reflect their ideals. Emphasizing our dedication to ethical sourcing and sustainable procedures allows Oasis Brew to recruit and retain a devoted customer base that values environmental responsibility.

2. Cultural Appreciation for Coffee

Coffee has a big place in Saudi social culture, creating a strong market for our products. Coffee is firmly established in Saudi culture, representing hospitality and tradition (Euromonitor International, 2023). This cultural affinity for coffee generates a significant demand for high-quality coffee experiences. Oasis Brew can capitalize on this cultural connection by providing distinctive, locally inspired coffee flavors and cultivating a community-centric environment.

3. Lifestyle Trends

There is a rising preference for premium and distinctive experiences, which aligns with our business approach. According to Pine and Gilmore's (1998) experience economy hypothesis, people prefer memorable experiences above items. This trend is reflected in the increasing demand for specialty coffee shops that provide distinct and

individualized experiences. Oasis Brew can capitalize on this trend by creating a unique atmosphere, sponsoring community activities, and offering customized coffee blends.

- **Technological Factors**

1. **Advances in Coffee Technology**

Innovations in coffee brewing and roasting can improve both product quality and operational efficiency. Precision grinders, high-efficiency espresso machines, and sophisticated roasting procedures are examples of technological developments in coffee equipment that allow for higher consistency and quality while preparing coffee. Adopting these technologies allows us to increase our product offerings and optimize operations, resulting in a better customer experience. Staying on top of technical innovations and incorporating them into our operations will be critical to sustaining a competitive advantage.

2. **Digital Marketing**

Using social media and digital platforms allows us to successfully reach and engage our target audience. David Aaker's (2009) brand equity model highlights the necessity of developing strong brand recognition and loyalty. Social media campaigns, influencer relationships, and content marketing are all examples of digital marketing methods that can help brands increase visibility and engagement. Oasis Brew can establish a strong online presence and cultivate a loyal following by utilizing digital technologies to communicate our company story and engage with customers.

3. **Sustainable Practices**

Technology facilitates the use of environmentally friendly materials and processes, which supports our sustainability goals. Paul Hawken, Amory Lovins, and L. Hunter Lovins (1999) promote the use of green technologies to create sustainable business practices. Sustainable packaging innovations, energy-efficient equipment, and trash reduction measures can all help to reduce our environmental impact. Implementing these technologies is consistent with our commitment to sustainability and appeals to environmentally concerned consumers, enhancing our brand's reputation as a leader in sustainable practices.

Funding Strategy

To fund its first operations and future expansion, Oasis Brew Coffee House will use a balanced mix of loan and equity funding. This balanced approach assures sufficient cash while retaining operational control and engaging stakeholders who share the company's mission. Given the dynamic nature of global markets and changing consumer preferences, our funding strategy is tailored to current global requirements and trends, with a focus on sustainability and community engagement.

Debt Financing

1. Bank Loans

Securing bank loans is a classic and practical way to fund initial capital expenses such as location acquisition, equipment procurement, and inventory. Bank loans have various advantages:

- **Liquidity without Ownership Dilution:** Bank loans give the liquidity required to begin operations while not diluting ownership holdings. This is critical for keeping control of the company and its strategic direction (Brigham, 2016).
- **Fixed payback Schedule:** Loans usually have fixed payback schedules, which allows for more predictable financial planning. This can improve the effectiveness of cash flow management (Gitman *et al.*, 2015).
- **Interest Tax Shield:** Debt interest payments are tax deductible, which can reduce the company's overall tax burden while increasing profitability (Modigliani & Miller, 1963).

Bank loans are especially appealing in Saudi Arabia because of low interest rates and supportive banking regulations aimed at promoting SME growth. The Saudi banking system, which is supported by the government's Vision 2030 project, provides a variety of credit packages specialized to SMEs (Saudi Arabia Monetary Authority, 2021).

Furthermore, global financial institutions are prioritizing sustainable investments. By highlighting our commitment to sustainability, Oasis Brew may be able to obtain green loans, which are financial products that fund environmentally responsible enterprises. These loans frequently have lower interest rates or other favorable terms, providing an additional incentive to align our business with global sustainability objectives (Banga, 2019).

2. Government Grants

Government subsidies are crucial for funding SMEs, particularly in economies that value diversification and entrepreneurship. Numerous grants and financial aid programs are available to support new enterprises as part of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030.

- **Non-Repayable Funding:** Unlike loans, grants do not need repayment, easing the financial strain on companies and allowing them to better deploy resources (Brush, 2008).
- **Support for Innovation and Sustainability:** Many awards are intended to encourage creative and sustainable company practices, which aligns perfectly with Oasis Brew's emphasis on sustainability and community engagement (Hall & Lerner, 2010).
- **Increased Credibility:** Receiving a government grant can boost a company's credibility, making it simpler to seek more investment from other sources (Mason & Harrison, 1996).

Navigating the application processes and satisfying specified requirements are required to take advantage of these awards, which Oasis Brew is uniquely positioned to achieve due to its strong emphasis on sustainability and local community benefit.

Globally, governments are progressively backing enterprises that promote environmental sustainability and social responsibility. Programs like the European Union's Green Deal, as well as equivalent initiatives in other regions, offer grants and subsidies to encourage sustainable corporate practices. Oasis Brew can have access to a broader range of funding options by aligning its business model with these global aims (Tutak *et al*, 2021).

3. Monsha'at Sharia Financing

The Monsha'at Authority provides Sharia-compliant finance alternatives designed exclusively for Saudi SMEs. These financing methods are consistent with Islamic financial principles, which restrict interest payments and instead emphasize profit-sharing and asset-based financing (Maspul, 2023).

- **Ethical Financing:** Sharia-compliant financing follows ethical investment standards and avoids actions that hurt society. This is consistent with Oasis Brew's dedication to social responsibility (Iqbal & Mirakhor, 2011).
- **Profit-Sharing Models:** Rather than typical interest-based loans, Sharia financing frequently employs profit-sharing agreements (Mudarabah) or cost-plus financing (Murabaha). This lowers the financial strain on the business in its early phases (Obaidullah, 2005).
- **Asset-Based Security:** Sharia financing frequently needs tangible assets as collateral, making it more accessible for firms with large physical investments like equipment and inventory (Ahmed, 2011).

Monsha'at's assistance can give Oasis Brew with the financing it requires while adhering to ethical financial practices, further integrating the company with local cultural and religious values.

Equity Financing

1. Angel Investors

Angel investors are wealthy individuals who provide funds to enterprises in exchange for ownership stock or convertible debt. They provide not only financial resources, but also significant knowledge and connections.

- **Risk Capital:** Angel investors are willing to take on more risk than traditional financiers, making them appropriate for high-growth firms with unclear short-term returns (Wiltbank *et al.*, 2009).
- **Strategic Guidance and Mentorship:** In addition to financial help, angel investors frequently provide strategic advice, industry experience, and mentorship, which can be extremely beneficial to a fledgling business (Van Osnabrugge & Robinson, 2000).

- Networking prospects: Angel investors can provide access to their networks, allowing for partnerships, business development prospects, and other investment rounds (Sohl, 2003).

Attracting angel investors who care about sustainability and specialty coffee will guarantee that Oasis Brew not only receives the financing it requires, but also aligns with investors who share its goal and beliefs. This approach is consistent with the growing global trend of impact investing, in which investors attempt to provide social and environmental effect in addition to financial returns (Bugg-Levine & Emerson, 2011).

2. Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a method of obtaining funds that involves the combined efforts of a large number of individual investors, generally through internet platforms such as Kickstarter or Indiegogo.

- funds Access: Crowdfunding allows for large funds without the requirement for traditional finance techniques. This democratizes the investing process, allowing enterprises to reach a larger pool of possible investors (Belleflamme *et al.*, 2014).
- Market Validation: A successful crowdfunding campaign acts as proof of concept and market validation, indicating demand for the product or service. This has the potential to attract additional traditional investment (Mollick, 2014).
- Network Building: Crowdfunding contributes to the growth of a network of early adopters and brand evangelists. These fans are frequently engaged and can provide useful feedback, supporting the brand through word-of-mouth (Ordanini *et al.*, 2011).
- Marketing and Exposure: Crowdfunding campaigns naturally promote marketing efforts because platforms frequently include built-in audiences and media attention that can raise visibility (Gerber *et al.*, 2012).

Oasis Brew can raise funds by beginning a crowdfunding campaign while also creating a loyal client base and increasing market awareness. This strategy is consistent with the global trend of community-supported firms, as well as the growing consumer need for openness and engagement in the businesses they support (Schwienbacher & Larralde, 2010).

Oasis Brew Coffee House intends to build a strong financial foundation that will support its purpose of providing sustainable, high-quality coffee while also encouraging community engagement. This hybrid method ensures access to cash while keeping strategic control and establishing a supportive network of investors and clients. The combination of sustainable practices and community-focused projects corresponds with global needs and trends, increasing the likelihood of long-term success and influence.

Conclusion

Oasis Brew Coffee House is set to transform the specialty coffee scene in Buraidah, Saudi Arabia, with a strategic blend of sustainability, cultural authenticity, and community

involvement. Leveraging market theories like Porter's Five Forces, Competitive Advantage Theory, and the Resource-Based View (RBV), we are equipped to tackle competitive challenges and harness our unique strengths for enduring success. Our financial projections indicate a strong growth trajectory driven by rising demand for ethically produced, high-quality coffee, with profitability anticipated by the end of Year 1 and expansion to five locations within five years.

Looking ahead, our franchising strategy will enable rapid market expansion while maintaining operational excellence and brand integrity. By Year 10, we expect significant consolidated sales and net profit, positioning us as a leading player in the specialty coffee industry. Oasis Brew Coffee House is more than a business; it is a movement towards a sustainable, community-centered coffee culture. Our innovative strategy and vision set us to lead the market, offering exceptional value to consumers, stakeholders, and the environment. As we move forward, Oasis Brew will establish new standards for excellence and sustainability in the global coffee market.

Our comprehensive financial strategy, combining debt and equity financing, ensures stability while fostering strategic control and stakeholder engagement. Bank loans provide liquidity without ownership dilution, aligning with favorable banking regulations and global sustainability trends. Government grants through Vision 2030 and Monsha'at's Sharia-compliant financing offer ethical, non-repayable funds, reinforcing our commitment to social responsibility. Attracting angel investors brings essential capital, strategic guidance, and valuable networks, while crowdfunding broadens our investor base and builds loyalty. Oasis Brew's holistic approach, integrating sustainability, premiumization, and community engagement, positions us for success in Saudi Arabia's competitive specialty coffee market. We are prepared for sustainable growth and considerable community impact by constantly responding to market conditions and using our unique assets, while also setting new standards for quality and social responsibility.

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